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DELIVERABLE REPORT

MINING THE FUTURE® INNOVATION CHALLENGE RESULTS

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Abstract:

A report that gives the outcome and results of the innovation challenge. The deliverable comprises a communication action (event, press release, media report), a technical summary and evaluation of the eligible submissions and a description of the results.

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Delivery Slip

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1. COMPETITION OVERVIEW

The Future Circular Collider (FCC) project envisages the construction of a large-scale Research Infrastructure that is based on a new, 100 km long, quasi-circular particle collider. This particle accelerator would be placed in an underground structure that consists of a tunnel, alcoves at regular intervals, large caverns and access shafts. These facilities would be between 150 and 350 metres underground. The construction project would generate about 9 million m³ of excavated materials. A large quantity of these materials is molasse, a heterogeneous, sedimentary rock frequently found in the Geneva basin.

The Mining the Future® Competition (the Competition) has been launched by MUL and CERN to identify credible means for the innovative re-use of the molasse materials that are expected to be encountered during the construction phase, in order to help reduce the amount of excavated material that will have to be disposed in landfills.

A Judging Panel of internationally renowned experts from subsurface-engineering, excavation materials re-use, and innovation management judged the Competition over a period of around one and a half years to select the most promising application(s).

The winner of the Competition has been awarded financial assistance for services required to advance the technology readiness level (TRL) of the proposed technologies, in terms of carrying out further needed tests and analysis activities for the proposed re-use approach in laboratories. This procedure aims at bringing the new product, service or process to market.

The submission of applications to the Competition started on 30 April 2021. The deadline for submission of applications to the Competition was 31 October 2021. The competition was structured in the following phases:

- Phase 1:
 - o Submission of the applications (30.04.21- 31.10.21)
 - o Evaluation phase for the selection of the most promising applications (01.11.21- 31.12.21)
- Phase 2:
 - o Advancement on technology readiness of the selected proposals (from TRL3 to TRL 4)
 - o Evaluation phase (01.01.22- 31.01.22)
 - o Announcement of the Winner(s) of the competition (August 2022)

An award ceremony (27 September 2022) closed the event.

At the deadline of October 31st, 2021, the competition had brought forward 12 eligible proposals. Four of these were selected for phase 2. These proposals were:

- CER3N: Recycle, Reinvent, Revalorize - Molassic excavated materials by harnessing digital & sorting tech. (Leading institute: AMBERG)
Focusing on the challenge of heterogeneity of molasse, Amberg and its partners propose to sort, identify and break down the excavated debris into materials of known composition for future use in projects.
- Molasse is the new ore (Leading institute: BG Ingénieurs)
To overcome the challenge of the undefined petrographic composition of molasse, the consortium led by BG Ingénieurs proposes to use online flow analysis, already used in cement plants, to immediately identify the excavated materials for further processing.
- From Molasse to brick (Leading institute: Briques Technic Concept)
The BTC and Arcadis consortium proposes to recover and reuse 300,000 cubic metres of molasse for further processing into raw earth bricks that can eventually be used to construct one million square metres of load-bearing walls.
- From Wastes to soil: Mineral Waste Reclamation to Fertile soil materials (Leading institute: Edaphos)

The consortium led by Edaphos, consisting of soil engineers and mechanical engineers, proposes to process the traditionally landfilled molasse into topsoil-like material using a process called "soil formulation".

Figure 1 – Members of the 4 finalist's consortia and speakers on stage at the award ceremony

The proposals were then evaluated over a matter of months by the jury of experts, who chose a consortium to crown during the award ceremony set for the 27th of September 2022.

Members of the four consortia were invited to the award ceremony at the Globe of Science and Innovation in Meyrin, Switzerland to present their proposals to an audience of 120 people from CERN and other organisations linked to the FCC Feasibility study. At the end of the ceremony, each of the members present received a certificate of completion which attested to their participation in the competition. The winning proposal was awarded a trophy designed and assembled at CERN, with local stone and recycled plastic, which represented the material excavated from the tunnel. The three other shortlisted proposals were each awarded a smaller version of the same trophy.

Figure 2 – Concept for the design of the trophy by Melchior Myard

The award ceremony was held on September 27th, 2022, at the Globe of Science and Innovation in CERN. The event featured an introduction by FCC Study leader Michael Benedikt. This opening talk was followed by talks by Patricia Postigo McLaughlin from the European commission on the EC’s role in research and innovation, and by Johannes Gutleber from FCC’s project office at CERN and Robert Galler from the University of Leoben, respectively on the challenge of the competition as well as on its scope and goals.

Figure 3 – Michael Benedikt giving his welcome talk during the award ceremony

After the introduction, the four shortlisted consortia presented their proposals in fifteen minutes each.

After the presentation, two additional talks were given, by Raphaël Bello (CERN Director for Finance and Human Resources) and Christian Holzleitner (Head of Unit for Land Use and Finance for Innovation, Directorate-General for Climate Action, European Commission).

The winner was then announced by Prof. Robert Galler. *Molasse is the new ore*, the consortium led by BG Ingénieurs Conseils took first prize.

The ceremony ended with a cocktail reception where the contest participants, jury members and guests could exchange in an informal environment.

Figure 4 – The consortium led by BG Ingénieurs Conseils, on stage to collect the 1st place trophy for their proposal: “Molasse is the new ore”

The ceremony was streamed via Zoom for invited guests who could not make it to CERN and filmed to be published later, on the event’s indico page. It was also live tweeted on the FCC study twitter account. The results were announced on all FCC social media profiles.

A press release relating the events of the competition has been sent to tunnelling associations and newspapers/magazines. An article was also published on the news section of the FCC website as well as in issue 41 of

CERN's *Accelerating News* and on CERN's website. The competition result will also appear in the November/December issue of the *CERN Courier*.

A presentation summarizing the competition and the related innovative proposals will be provided at the tunnel conference in Austria.

Figure 5 – Headline of the article about the competition on the FCC study website

Figure 6 – Facebook post announcing the winner of the competition

Figure 7 – LinkedIn post announcing the winner of the competition on the FCC Study's page

Figure 8 – Post announcing the winner on the FCC study’s Instagram

The results of the competition are now being scrutinized for application in the FCC feasibility study. The MATEX working group, created in the framework of the WP3 of the FCCIS project (H2020), who is developing the concept for an excavation material management plan, is piloting the study for the applicability of the proposals presented by the winner and the other 3 finalists.

2. APPLICATION OPEN FOR SUBMISSION

The submission of applications to the Competition started on 30 April 2021. The deadline for submission of applications to the Competition was 31 October 2021. All the information related to the Competition can be found on the website: cern.ch/miningthefuture:

How to apply?

Applicants can submit one or more applications by **31 October 2021**.

More information about eligibility, evaluation criteria and the contest proceedings is available in the competition guidelines.

Download the competition guidelines

+ Submit your application

DEADLINE
31.10

Figure 9- Extract from the competition website

Who can apply?

The Mining the Future competition is open to all persons and organisations eligible to participate in Horizon 2020:

- Individual persons
- Non-profit, academic and higher education organisations
- International European Interest Organisations (IEIOs)
- For-profit organisations, including companies and consortia that have their corporate

Applicants should present a promising and credible solution for the reuse of excavated molasse materials. The proof-of-concept for the technology should already have been demonstrated in laboratory conditions (TRL3). The technology should credibly be on track to be turned into a product, service or industrial process by 2030 (TRL 9).

Figure 10- Extract from the competition website

Mining the Future® – Challenge-based International Innovation Competition

30 April 2021 to 31 October 2021
Europe/Zurich timezone

- Overview
- Competition website
- Participation Guidelines
- Technical Documentation
- Application and participation forms
- Apply now!**
- Contact
- ✉ fccis-mtf-support@cern.ch

Competition timeline

Application	30 April 2021 to 31 October 2021
Evaluation Phase 1	01 November 2021 to 31 December 2021
Evaluation Phase 2	01 January 2022 to 31 July 2022
Announcement of the winner(s)	August 2022
Award ceremony	October 2022

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Figure 11 – Indico site for application (<https://indico.cern.ch/e/MiningTheFuture>)

3. EVALUATION BOARD

The “Mining the Future®” Competition was held from April 2021 to August 2022. The Judging Panel was composed of ten international experts from around the globe in the fields of geology, subsurface engineering, materials science, innovation management and environmental management. The first phase lasted from April to October 2021 for submission of proposals and was followed by a reviewing and pre-selecting period for the proposed technologies based on the submitted documentation. During the second phase, that lasted until mid-2022, the judging panel members identified one or more winners based on interactive Q&A sessions with the submitting teams using videoconferencing technology.

Table 1 Members of the judging panel

Name	Affiliation, Country
Robert GALLER	Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria
Guillaume ATTARD	CEREMA, France
Jacques BURDIN	Jacques BURDIN Ingénieur Conseil, France
Laetitia D’ALOIA SCHWARTZENTRUBER	CETU, France
Herbert EINSTEIN	MIT Boston, Civil and Environmental Engineering, United States
Klaus MARHOLD	Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien, Austria
Manuela ROCCA	TELT, Italy
Severin SEIFERT	Fraunhofer, Germany
Cedric THALMANN	B+ G Betontechnologie + Materialbewirtschaftung AG, Switzerland
Alexander WYSS	SIMATEC Maschinenbau, Switzerland

Figure 12 – Presentation of the jury members on the website

Figure 13 – Introduction to the Chair of the Jury on the website

Figure 14 – Members of the Jury on stage at the award ceremony

4. MARKETING CAMPAIGN

4.1. OBJECTIVES

Together with the website and the application form, a marketing campaign was launched on 30 April 2021. The goals of the campaign were to attract quality participants to the competition, resulting in several solid proposals, and to raise awareness of the competition and the FCC project as a whole to reach a broader audience. The objectives were to promote the competition and to support the communications for the FCC project.

Figure 15 – Extract from the English version of the video clip

Figure 16 – Extract from the French video clip

4.2. AUDIENCE

The target audiences are:

- Geology experts, Civil Engineers, Tunneling and Construction Industry in Europe and globally
- Innovators, Technology Transfer Officers, Futurists
- Scientists from other fields
- Funding agencies in Europe and from CERN's Member States and Non-Member States
- Science & Technology journalists
- Policy makers, at regional, national, and European level.

4.3. TOOLS AND CHANNELS

The marketing campaign included weekly social media posts, stakeholder toolkits, promotion through different channels (technical, non-technical magazines).

4.3.1. Website

The central content piece of the campaign is the contest website cern.ch/miningthefuture.

Figure 2 – Welcome page of the competition website

4.3.2. Social media

The following social media played a key role in the Mining the Future contest:

- Twitter is an interesting platform since it combines a prevalence of professionals, politicians and media representatives with advanced targeting and sponsoring possibilities. Twitter was the most effective tool in reaching potential applicants and the wider scientific community efficiently.
- Facebook is the platform with the densest penetration across target audiences, demographics, and regions. It was used to reach the broader public, with any submissions generated through this platform considered by-catch.
- LinkedIn: even more so than Twitter, LinkedIn allowed us to reach professional and expert audiences that might submit an application.

4.3.3. Press release

It was planned to have two press releases (in French, English, and German) during the campaign:

- At the start of the campaign, a press release aimed at technical media to gather attention for the competition with our primary target audience of potential applicants.
- After the final event, a press release to announce the winners of the competition.